

INVESTIGATING A MEDITERRANEAN WETLAND CATCHMENTS HYDRODYNAMICS THROUGH TRACER HYDROLOGY

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Wetland catchments that experience a Mediterranean climate have been identified as areas of concern (i.e., water quality, availability, and hydrodynamics) under the ever-growing anthropogenic and climatic forcings. Although, the majority of these climates are located in southern Europe, Western Australia and Northern Africa, one such region exists in the Western Cape of South Africa. This semi-arid region is dependent on winter rainfalls to sustain domestic, industrial, and ecological water demands. During recent droughts, surface water resources were stressed almost to depletion, fostering an increased dependence on groundwater resources. This pressure is exerted on both the hydrological system and ecosystem function, leading to water security issues. Sustainable water management in a perturbed hydrological system requires an understanding of the system's baseline functioning as well as the degree and rate at which the system is changing. Hydrological tracers have proven effective tools to constrain such behaviours in modified catchments that are affected by climate change. A tracer-based approach was applied to the highly modified Eerste River Catchment in the Western Cape, to assess the catchment's water origin and dynamics that terminate in the estuarine Macassar Wetland. Over time wastewater treatment plant developments, informal/formal domains, and water diversion schemes have negatively impacted the wetland. To understand the watershed hydrological regimes and stability of the associated wetland in a changing climate scenario, three sample campaigns were conducted during the dry and wet seasons in March, June, and September 2023. Shallow and deep aquifers were targeted for tritium (55 samples), tritium helium age (4 sites) and dissolved noble gas (10 sites) analyses. Additionally, 5 surface water sites were sampled for dissolved noble gases. Tracer data effectively identified areas of recharge, lateral flow, and discharge of groundwaters. Furthermore, when simulated against localised lumped parameter models it enabled a revision of the catchment's conceptual groundwater-surface water interaction mechanics as well as determining a residence time distribution between recharge and discharge information. This study's hydrogeological tracer findings can provide insights transferable to analogous Mediterranean environments for effective and efficient hydrology diagnosis to promote enhanced water resources management and wetland support, particularly under forecasted drought episodes. **Keywords:** Tritium, Noble Gases, Residence Time, Wetland, Mediterranean, Groundwater, Surface water.